

Putting the ‘focus’ into focus groups

by Carol Kennedy Gardiner

carol.kennedygardiner64@mail.dcu.ie <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9464-9494>

Dublin City University, D09 DY00 Dublin, Ireland

Abstract

How important is one’s ‘focus’ within focus interviews and what should one be focusing on? This study establishes one of two methodological approaches used to examine experiences of those who have been given a diagnosis of Developmental Co-ordination Disorder (DCD) as they journey through post-primary school from the perspective of a novice researcher. The research took phenomenological approach (Vagle, 2018; Valentine et al., 2018), exploring human experiences through participant descriptions of their ‘lived’ experiences (Farrell, 2020). It describes these experiences and the meaning that participants attribute to experiences of inclusion, informed by the importance of listening to learner voices (Edmonds, 2012). This article outlines the use of focus groups to examine key and reoccurring themes for participants in the study. It examines how one ought to keep the focus within the focus groups.

Keywords: Focus Groups; Developmental Co-ordination Disorder; Learner Voice

Three Key Highlights

- How the novice educational researcher can ensure that there is a focus in their focus groups is examined.
- The exploration of the experiences of learners who have been given a diagnosis of Developmental Co-Ordination Disorder (DCD) is described.
- Methods for capturing authentic learner voice in educational research are considered.

Introduction

This article explores how a novice educational researcher can ensure that there is focus within their focus groups. The readers will be provided with an argument for the purpose, rationale and philosophical underpinnings of using focus groups as a methodology. The importance of focus groups to consolidate learning and key themes will be outlined as it has been changed and continues to change throughout the research as themes and topics develop. Finally, there will be a presentation of the ethical considerations that need to be borne in mind as one

embarks on the journey of research, including participant recruitment, data collection instruments and the challenges that have emerged along the way.

Regarding the context in which these will be examined, the research study in question aims to explore the experiences of learners diagnosed with Developmental Co-ordination Disorder (DCD) who were enrolled in Irish mainstream post-primary schools using research, a Critical Disability Studies (CDS) perspective. It will capture their perceptions and experiences of senior cycle provision and use these to identify how their access to, participation in and benefit from authentic, inclusive education can be enriched (Merton et al, 1990). From an essentialist perspective, Developmental Co-ordination Disorder (DCD) is thought to be a neurological disorder which affects between 5% and 6% of the population of learners (American Psychiatric Association (APA), 1994). The diagnosis of DCD is distinct and separate from other diagnoses of neurological conditions (Meachon et al., 2022). This study uses a CDS perspective which sees diagnosis of disability as a label bestowed on a person rather than something that they necessarily want or need to make sense of their place in the world.

Initial decisions and underlying assumptions

In this research, it was decided that a qualitative method would work best to give a unique viewpoint on the topic (Denscombe, 2003). There are some areas of education which are dominated by one approach to research. As a result, some researchers worry that the research technologies are unclear (Newby, 2010). However, it was important to adopt a framework that addressed all aspects of the research questions (Cohen et al., 2007).

Why focus groups?

Essentially, a focus group is a group of people who come together to discuss a common topic of interest (Merton et al., 1990). Having their origin in market research in the 1970s, focus groups have evolved and changed (Hall, 2020). They are now a favourite of educational researchers as they help the researcher to gather a body of data from a number of different voices and perspectives (Morgan, 1996). Focus groups are the choice for this research for a number of reasons: they are made up of a triad of participants with a researcher to discuss a key topic in an environment that allows a *discussion* (rather than an interview) to occur. The researcher intended to gather a collective account of what life feels like for learners who have been given a diagnosis of DCD. Was the experience of everyone the same, or were there significant differences? What was the root cause of the difference for learners?

This research began with a number of semi-structured interviews where participants met with the researcher to discuss their post-primary school lived experiences (Merton et al., 1990). The subsequent focus group allowed the researcher to delve a little deeper into some of the emergent overall themes and some of the insights from those initial discussions (Morgan, 1996). The educational researcher was interested in finding out if the participants had the same sense of their experiences when discussing the topic in a larger group (Morgan & Krueger, 1993). The “synergy” within the group, which did not exist in the first phase of the research, was important in highlighting nuances and subtleties (Krueger & Casey, 2014). The intention was to use focus groups to add to what had already been discovered (Morgan, 1996).

In terms of methodology, it is important to be very clear when underlining the aim of the focus group. It is important that participants can answer the questions asked of them in a reliable way (Greenbaum, 1998). Krueger and Casey (2014) outline a five-point checklist for asking questions in a focus group. They point out the importance of the participant understanding the question, knowing and being able to articulate the answer. They also highlight the importance of the environment in allowing the respondent to answer honestly. Equally, they ought to be willing to give the information desired of them. In order to do this, researchers suggest that participants should receive a one page outline of the project with its research aim and objectives (Greenbaum, 1998). The researcher in this study used a one page plain language statement to outline the research.

How has the focus changed because of the interviews?

The research needed to move from questions about individual lived experiences in the semi-structured interviews to more universal questions about ‘inclusion’, all the while bearing in mind the importance of the CDS perspective. One of the key issues identified for early career researchers in undertaking focus groups is the failure to plan for analysis (Krueger & Casey, 2014). Thus the focus groups challenged the participants to consider how they and their peers experienced inclusion and exclusion in school, from the perspective of a learner who had been given a diagnosis of DCD. It also challenged the researcher to consider how to best capture and report diverse ideas within a single group.

In planning for the focus groups, it was important to carefully plan what was going to be asked within the groups (Krueger & Casey, 2014). While the questions appeared natural and unplanned, they were the focus of careful thinking and reflection (Krueger & Casey, 2014).

The biggest challenge for the groups and the focus was on the key question, “what does inclusion really mean?” This question called into focus some of the key themes and concerns of the research but also challenged participants to examine their experience through a different lens. It really did help to put the focus back into my focus groups. This was the question which generated the most debate and reflection. What follows is a discussion focusing on the key findings that were constructed as a result of the focus group in relation to DCD.

Developmental Co-ordination Disorder (DCD)

Lived experiences

In some ways, the focus group can provide reassurance concerning what learners already identified as lived experiences with DCD (Neubauer, Witkop & Varpio, 2019). This is one of the key rationale for conducting this further phase of methodological enquiry (Bignotti & Le Roux, 2020). Equally, the focus groups allowed the researcher to hear new insights prompted by the communal discussion and sharing of experiences (Dodds & Hess, 2020). Sometimes, it was the case that through the focus groups, inherent themes that did not occur in the semi-structured interviews became a key focus of the discussion, causing the researcher to review some of the data and reflect again on the key research question. It was very interesting to reflect on what participants defined as ‘inclusion’ and how they expressed this equally.

Perspectives on disability within an inclusive context

The principles of inclusive education call into question traditional views of disability based on categorisation and measuring differences (Amanze & Nkhoma, 2020; Brussino, 2020; Tiernan, 2021). Yet there is compelling evidence, both from my initial data collection and from the literature, that those working in schools view DCD from the medical model perspective (Kirby, 2004; Shyman, 2016; Hunt et al., 2021) within which DCD is characterised as a neurological disorder.

In terms of the research, the educational researcher chose to use a CDS perspective. There is an awareness of the challenges of a diagnosis from a medical and social viewpoint, which is quite often the perspective that learners encounter in education and is important within this research (Shakespeare, 2013). The CDS view offers an alternative perspective on disability (Watson, 2012). It asserts that, far from being a medical or essential phenomenon, disability (including subcategories of this, such as DCD) is a socially and culturally engendered

concept (Teodoro, 2020) that allows particular types of naturally occurring human variation to be viewed as deficits (Shildrick, 2019).

CDS asks why and in whose interests this occurs (Meekosha & Shuttleworth, 2009); this was one of the key focus questions in the focus groups. It was the cornerstone of the research. Once the data collection was complete, the researcher employed a CDS perspective to analyse and interpret the views of participants in order to:

1. Make sense of their experiences
2. Analyse what these tell us about the, policies, structures, practices and relations of power that currently exist in schools around the inclusion of learners assessed with DCD
3. Chart a course towards improved and more equitable provision for these learners.

The use of the focus groups added increased depth and rigour to the researchers' effort to address these analytical aims.

Phenomenological approach

Learner Voice

In line with the phenomenological tradition of inquiry, it was intended that this research would shed light on the lived experiences of inclusion and exclusion described by those who have experienced what it feels like to be a post-primary learner. Focus groups offered an opportunity to use the perspectives of learners who have experienced what life was like in the post-primary context to make suggestions about how their experiences can be improved (Niens & Reilly, 2012; Prunty, 2016). They also allowed participants to share their experiences with others and reflect on whether this was a communal experience or exclusive to the participant in their context and their own school (Krueger & Casey, 2014).

Allowing learners a voice and a place to share their experiences was very important as the bedrock of this research (Morgan, 1996). The researcher felt that the inequity gap between those allowed to speak in post-primary education and those silenced is very important and telling in terms of inclusion. It was also hoped that examining how learner voices might be used to begin and continue a conversation about the needs of learners who have been given a diagnosis of DCD would be valuable. The format of the focus group allowed room for more exploration of these key themes from the perspective of all of the participants, which engendered some animated debate and discussion.

Ethical considerations using focus groups

There are a number of ethical considerations that need to be addressed before using focus groups. A small sample of these are presented here alongside a brief description as to how these were addressed by the research in the current study.

Moderator

Researchers suggest that novice researchers must carefully manage the focus group (Wilson, 1997). The participants must be invited to share their own experiences with the researcher. They are experts in a different way – they have lived the experience of inclusion and exclusion as participants who have been given the label of DCD by society. Greenbaum (1998) explains that technical expertise in conducting focus groups is much more important than research methodology.

Whether one uses a moderator or not, there are three key areas that a researcher needs to be aware of. One needs to be cognizant of methodological mistakes (Morgan & Krueger, 1993; Smithson, 2000). For this reason, it is important to be aware of the aims of the research (Kitzinger, 1995; Breen, 2006; Acocella, 2012). Some researchers recommend writing down research objectives and sharing them with the participants at the outset of the focus group (Greenbaum, 1998).

Secondly, researchers caution that some novice researchers make mistakes with implementation (Smithson, 2000). Krueger and Casey (2014) highlight the importance of being aware of the questions and how they are asked. Key questions are critical to the overall research (Kitzinger, 1995; Breen, 2006; Falter et al., 2022). The moderator needs to be very cognizant of the importance of these questions (Morgan, 1996; Litosseliti, 2003). They are some of the first to be articulated and some of the most important (Morgan, 1996; Acocella, 2012; Wilkinson, 2015). However, one does not begin with the key questions. It is important to give participants time to relax in the focus group (Krueger, 1997). Opening questions are easy to answer and allow the participants to find their voice in the focus group. The opening question used in these focus groups was “Tell us your pseudonym, what sort of a post-primary school you went to and what you most enjoy doing when you are relaxing”. The questions were easy to address; they allowed all the participants to say something and to make connections with each other. Transition questions followed the introduction, creating a link between the introduction and the key questions (Krueger & Casey, 2014). Final questions helped participants to think about what had been said.

Participant recruitment

A total of twelve learners were recruited to participate in this research. Each of these learners had been given a diagnosis of DCD. The participants were eighteen or nineteen years old, either just finishing their post-primary education or have completed their post-primary education. They were recruited through an invitation circulated by Dyspraxia DCD Ireland. The young adults decided to approach the researcher, indicating their potential involvement. Krueger and Casey (2014) warn that recruitment takes much longer than anticipated. It is, without doubt, the most nerve-wracking part of the data collection process as one worries about getting sufficient participation as well as remaining cognizant of the fact that one needs the “correct” participants (Shaffir & Stebbins, 1990). Morgan (1996) recommends over-recruiting by 20% to allow for participant drop-out. In terms of the focus group, it was important to be sure that the participants met the requirements of the research project (Morgan & Krueger, 1993; Morgan, 1996; Krueger, 1997; Krueger & Casey, 2014; Hall, 2020).

The focus groups were typically made up of three participants, with the educational researcher and a moderator. The researcher wanted to encourage discussion and sharing. It was important that there was a space and a time to ensure that everyone’s voice was heard – this was one of the key roles of the moderator (Krueger & Casey, 2014). The researcher was aware of the limitations of the small group, which meant that a smaller pool of ideas were generated (Smithson, 2000; Krueger & Casey, 2014). However, considering the fact that everyone was given a chance to share and explore, it was felt that the data generated was rich.

Data collection instruments

Zoom, a social communication platform, was chosen to conduct these focus groups. There were a number of reasons for choosing Zoom (Falter et al., 2022). To begin with, both the educational researcher and all the participants were familiar with the platform, which allowed everyone to feel a little more comfortable in the space (Rosser et al., 2011). The idea of being comfortable sharing within the group is vital to the success of the focus group (Lathen & Laestadius, 2021).

Participants chose a pseudonym for themselves, which they will write on screen (Falter et al., 2022). The job of the researcher was simply to explain the technical aspect of how the participant could do that (Smithson, 2000). Researchers suggest a tech check before the focus groups begin (Falter et al., 2022). Then the researcher should begin the session with an

introduction, followed by a warm-up, the contents and summary (Morgan & Krueger, 1993; Morgan, 1996, 2018). Krueger and Casey (2014) remind the researcher to take time at the end of the focus group to review the key findings with the group and to invite participants to add what they think may have been left out or incomplete.

Challenges

One of the biggest challenges in this research and in preparation for the focus groups was re-aligning the focus of the researcher. Having completed the first phase of the research, putting the ‘focus’ back into the focus group was a challenge – it was important that the research questions became the focus once again. Returning to the conceptual research framework and revisiting the plan to take a CDS perspective to analyse and interpret the participants’ views and experiences were key parts of this planning (Meekosha & Shuttleworth, 2009). The plan was to link how the experiences informed one about policies, structures, practices and relations of power that currently exist in post-primary schools around the inclusion of learners who have been given a diagnosis of DCD.

Dependability

Much is written in the literature for and against the dependability of the results of focus groups. Some critics claim that you cannot trust the results of a focus group (Morgan, 1996; Smithson, 2000). This assertion is based on the fact that some participants may not have the best interests of the research at heart. Others argue that, in fact, examining the processes of the focus group can often highlight whether the results are dependable (Smithson, 2000; Langer, 2007). Sometimes it is not the researcher’s fault or the participants’ but rather the overall planning and processes (Krueger & Casey, 2014). In terms of ensuring dependability of results, it is critical that there is a clear focus for the focus group with clear aims and outcomes.

Conclusion

This article explored how a novice educational researcher may ensure that there is ‘focus’ within focus groups. The readers were provided with an argument for the purpose, rationale and philosophical underpinnings of using focus groups as a methodology. The changing nature of focus groups was explored followed by a presentation of the ethical considerations when using focus groups. In this research, using a CDS perspective, the research explored the experiences of learners diagnosed with DCD, to make sense of their place in the world.

References

- Acocella, I., (2012) 'The focus groups in social research: advantages and disadvantages', *Quality & Quantity*, 46, pp.1125-1136.
- Amanze, N. and Nkhoma, S. eds., (2020) *Disability is not inability: A Quest for Inclusion and Participation of People with Disability in Society*. African Books Collective.
- American Psychiatric Association (APA) (1994) 'Motor Skill Disorder 315.40: Developmental Coordination Disorder', *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV)*. 4th Edn.
- Bignotti, A. and Le Roux, I., (2020) 'Which types of experience matter? The role of prior start-up experiences and work experience in fostering youth entrepreneurial intentions', *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(6), pp.1181-1198.
- Breen, R.L., (2006) 'A practical guide to focus-group research', *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 30(3), pp.463-475.
- Brussino, O., (2020). Mapping policy approaches and practices for the inclusion of students with special education needs, OECD.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K., 2007. *Research methods in education*. Routledge.
- Denscombe, M., (2003) *The good research guide*. Maidenhead. Open University.
- Dodds, S. and Hess, A.C., (2020) 'Adapting research methodology during COVID-19: lessons for transformative service research', *Journal of Service Management*, 32(2), pp. 203-217.
- Falter, M.M., Arenas, A.A., Maples, G.W., Smith, C.T., Lamb, L.J., Anderson, M.G., Uzzell, E.M., Jacobs, L.E., Cason, X.L., Griffis, T.A. and Polzin, M., (2022) 'Making room for Zoom in focus group methods: opportunities and challenges for novice researchers (during and beyond COVID-19)', *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 23(1), pp.1-27.
- Gladwell, M., (2005) *Blink*. Little, Brown and Company.
- Greenbaum, T.L., (1998) *The Handbook for Focus Group Research*. Sage Publications.
- Hall, J. N., (2020) *Focus Groups- Culturally Responsive Approaches for Qualitative Inquiry and Program Evaluation*. Myers Education Press.
- Hunt, J., Zwicker, J.G., Godecke, E. and Raynor, A., (2021) 'Awareness and knowledge of developmental coordination disorder: A survey of caregivers, teachers, allied health professionals and medical professionals in Australia', *Child: care, health and development*, 47(2), pp.174-183.
- Kirby, A., (2004) 'Is dyspraxia a medical condition or a social disorder?', *The British Journal of General Practice*, 54(498), pp.6.

- Kitzinger, J., (1995) 'Qualitative research: introducing focus groups', *British Medical Journal*, 311(7000), pp.299-302.
- Krueger, R.A., (1997) *Analysing and reporting focus group results*. Sage Publications.
- Krueger, R.A., Casey, M.A., (2014) *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*. Sage publications.
- Langer, J., 2007. Time-honored or time to go. *Quirk's Marketing Research Review*, pp.24-33.
- Lathen, L. and Laestadius, L., (2021) 'Reflections on online focus group research with low socio-economic status African American adults during COVID-19', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20. <https://doi-org.dcu.idm.oclc.org/10.1177/16094069211021713>
- Litosseliti, L., (2003) *Using focus groups in research*. A&C Black.
- Meekosha, H. and Shuttleworth, R. (2009) 'What's so 'critical' about critical disability studies?' *Australian Journal of Human Rights*, 15(1), pp.47-75.
- Merton, R.K., Fiske, M., and Kendall, P.L., (1990) *The Focused Interview*. 2nd Edn. Free Press.
- Morgan, D.L., (1996) *Focus groups as qualitative research*. Sage publications.
- Morgan, D. L., & Krueger, R. A. (1993). When to use focus groups and why. In D. L. Morgan (Ed.), *Successful focus groups: Advancing the state of the art* (pp. 3–19). Sage Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483349008.n1>
- Neubauer, B.E., Witkop, C.T. and Varpio, L., (2019) 'How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others', *Perspectives on medical education*, 8, pp. 90-97.
- Newby, P., (2010) *Research methods for education*. Pearson Education.
- Niens, U. and Reilly, J., (2012) 'Education for global citizenship in a divided society? Young people's views and experiences', *Comparative Education*, 48(1), pp.103-118.
- Prunty, M., (2016) 'Dyspraxia is more than just "clumsy child syndrome" it can cause emotional distress and anxiety throughout life', *The Conversation*, 11 November. Available: <https://theconversation.com/dyspraxia-is-more-than-just-clumsy-child-syndrome-it-can-cause-emotional-distress-and-anxiety-throughout-life-66948>
- Rosser, B.S., Wilkerson, J.M., Smolenski, D.J., Oakes, J.M., Konstan, J., Horvath, K.J., Kilian, G.R., Novak, D.S., Danilenko, G.P. and Morgan, R., (2011) 'The future of Internet-based HIV prevention: A report on key findings from the Men's INTERNET (MINTS-I, II)', in. *Sex Studies. AIDS and Behavior*, 15, pp.91-100.
- Shaffir, W. and Stebbins, R.A. eds (1990) *Experiencing fieldwork: An inside view of qualitative research*. Sage Publications.
- Shakespeare, T., (2013) *Disability rights and wrongs revisited*. Routledge.

Shildrick, M., 2019. Critical disability studies: Rethinking the conventions for the age of postmodernity. In *Routledge handbook of disability studies* (pp. 32-44). Routledge.

Shyman, E., (2016) 'The reinforcement of ableism: Normality, the medical model of disability, and humanism in applied behavior analysis and ASD', *Intellectual and developmental disabilities*, 54(5), pp.366-376.

Smithson, J., (2000) 'Using and analysing focus groups: limitations and possibilities', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 3(2), pp.103-119.

Teodoro, A., (2020) *Contesting the global development of sustainable and inclusive education: Education reform and the challenges of neoliberal globalization*. Routledge.

Tiernan, B., (2021) 'Inclusion versus full inclusion: implications for progressing inclusive education', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, pp.1-9.

Watson, N., (2012) 'Theorising the lives of disabled children: How can disability theory help?' *Children & Society*, 26(3), pp.192-202.

Wilkinson, S., (2015) *Focus groups. Qualitative psychology: a practical guide to research methods*. 3rd Edn. Sage Publications.

Wilson, V., (1997) 'Focus groups: a useful qualitative method for educational research?', *British Educational Research Journal*, 23(2), pp.209-224.